

**Fostering Improved Training Tools
For Responsible Research and Innovation
FIT4RRI**

Experiment 2 Report
Photonics (Optical Monitoring)
(Deliverable 3.3)

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Table of Contents

Definitions.....	4
Executive summary (key points)	5
1. Experiment description.....	5
1.1. Organiser	5
1.2. Aims and objectives	5
1.3. Selected RRI pillars.....	6
2. Internal stakeholders' description.....	6
3. External stakeholders' description.....	6
4. Initial questionnaire summary and results.....	6
4.1 Ethics internal responses.....	7
4.2 Ethics external responses.....	8
4.3 Science education internal responses.....	8
4.4 Science education external responses	9
5. Focus group outcome summary	9
6. Follow-up interview summary.....	10
7. Workshop summary	12
8. Second questionnaire summary	13
8.1 Ethics Internal responses	14
8.2 Ethics external responses.....	15
8.3 Science education internal responses	15
8.4 Science education external responses.....	16
9. Comparing the first and second questionnaire.	16
10. Lessons learnt.....	16
10.1 Main blockers of quadruple helix co-creation.....	17
10.2 Proposed consensus strategies and co-creation approaches/frameworks.....	17
10.3 Most relevant RRI practices from WP1 and WP2 for the experiment.....	17
10.4 Institutional changes required to fully embed the chosen RRI pillars	17
10.5 Policy support/changes required to properly embed RRI in the ongoing research with the involvement of the quadruple helix	18
10.6 Any issues/constraints notice during the experiment implementation (i.e procedural issues)	18
11 Next steps.....	18
Appendix A – Experiment KPIs.....	19

List of Tables

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation for the understanding and motivation of implementation of ethics and science education.....	7
Table 2: Mean and standard deviation for the understanding and motivation of implementation of ethics and science education.....	14

Definitions

N/A.

Executive summary (key points)

The project aimed to identify the understanding and opinions of internal and external stakeholders with regard to ethics and science education, using the RRI principals. The participants were asked to consider the ethical and science education implications of a monitoring system case study as well as drawing on their own experiences and opinions. Each participant was invited to fill out two questionnaire, one at start of the process and one at the end, attend a focus group and workshop and take part in a one-to-one interview. The results of the study show at the start there was a lack of understanding of why ethics was important and how to implement it effectively into a research project. By the end of the study most participants has a slight increase in ethical awareness and motivation to implement ethics however more support and clarity is still needed in this area. Furthermore the results suggest there was a widespread lack of understand of what is meant by science education. As a result of the workshop the participant now display a high increase in understanding and have developed the motivation to implement better science education for the benefit of society.

1. Experiment description

The experiment was carried out in The University of Liverpool with a mixture of internal (university staff) and external participants. We asked the participants to fill out self-report questionnaires to gain a benchmark of where their level of understanding was on the subjects of ethics and science education. They were then invited to take part in a focus group where collectively we discusses how to better embed the RRI principals into research projects. This is where the monitoring system case study was used to give the participants an understanding of the type of research projects we are working on. From this focus group we then conducted one-to-one interviews with each of the participants to reflect on what was discussed at the focus group and how this can be embedded into their current role. Also as part of the interview we asked the participant what they would like to see in the upcoming workshop and what they were hoping to learn from the event. Based on these answers a workshop was constructed for the participants to expand their knowledge and understanding of RRI, focusing on ethics and science education. Each participant was then asked to repeat the questionnaire to measure if there was a development in understanding.

1.1. Organiser

Professor Joseph Spencer, Dr Roberto Ferrero and Mary Jane Monaghan from The University of Liverpool.

1.2. Aims and objectives

- To explore and discuss ethical issues with various stakeholders and how they perceive these
- Identify other ethics related issues/challenges that impinge on the research
- Increase awareness of different perceptions and views of ethics

- Identify any weaknesses, misconceptions, omissions, barriers, communication issues etc. in Science Education within the research institution, industry and society.
- Explore the understanding and perceptions that stakeholder have of science education
- We hope to identify issues that can lead to the improvement in the way science education is delivered/communicated in the institution and community.

1.3. Selected RRI pillars

Ethics and Science Education.

2. Internal stakeholders' description

A selection of internal stakeholders were identified, these are all members of Staff from The University of Liverpool. Job roles range from PHD student, to researcher, to research support staff and members of the ethics board.

3. External stakeholders' description

External stakeholders are made up of, local small to medium business owners and managing directors, potential user/beneficiaries of the technology, Liverpool city council employees and NHS employees.

4. Initial questionnaire summary and results

Internal and external participants (n=13, external n=8, internal n=5) took part in a self-report questionnaire on FIT4RRI ethics and science education.

When thinking ethics the participants rated their understanding on a five point scale (1=not at all aware, 5= highly aware) answering three questions on their understanding of ethics the results show, external participants had a high level of ethics understanding (M=11.3) as well as internal participants also displaying a high level of understanding (M=14). The participants were asked, in the same way, their understanding of science education. For both internal (M=7.4) and external (M=9.5). The results show this was lower than their ethics understanding. The participants were then asked to rate their motivation of the implementation of ethics, internal (M=13.2) external (M=13.1) and their motivation of the implementation of science education, internal (M=10.4) external (M=11.3). The results show the motivation to implement ethics was higher than that of science education. As well as external motivation being higher on both than internal motivation.

Table one shows the mean and standard deviation for the understanding of ethics and science education, both internally and externally and the motivation to implement ethics and science education also both internally and externally.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation for the understanding and motivation of implementation of ethics and science education.

	Mean	SD
Understanding of ethics – External	11.3	2.9
Understanding of ethics – internal	14	1.7
Motivation to implement ethics – external	13.1	1.7
Motivation to implement ethics – internal	13.2	1.4
Understanding of science education – external	9.5	2.8
Understanding of science education – internal	7.4	1.6
Motivation to implement science education – external	11.3	2.3
Motivation to implement science education – internal	10.4	3.6

After each question the participant where asked to expand on their point score. Below is a summary of their responses.

4.1 Ethics internal responses

In the responses given there was some understanding of the internal ethical procedures, with some participants displaying extensive knowledge of ethics implantations as it is part of their role. Participants displayed an understanding of the importance of implanting ethics stating it is “pivotal to research”. As well as noting how they have seen an improvement in the engagement and enthusiasm for research ethics. It is agreed that the university has a robust ethics system in place, with deans, heads of departments and academic leadership, displaying motivation to implement high standards of research ethics. Participants understood the need for ethics describing it as “crucial”, also suggesting that without ethics there would be “no respect, no communication, and no relationship”.

Some academics who work in the ethics department suggest there is a number of researchers across disciplines, who do not have a basic understanding of why ethics is important. Furthermore, the participants suggest some staff at the university may see ethics as an unnecessary administrative barrier to conducting research. Even though it was noted that academic leadership was motivated to implement ethical research, commented was also the inconsistencies of this support at a school or departmental level. With some academics being encouraged to focus on publications as their contributions to ethics and integrity “cannot be recognised”. Moreover, it was stated in responses that there is limited knowledge of how to implement ethics, this is mainly from participants who were not directly involved with the process.

What is needed to improve understanding an awareness has increased according to some participants, however it is also stated that the depth of knowledge varies greatly among disciplines, and that raising awareness is not without its challenges. Participants noted that having an “under-resourced team and academics having a high workload” contributes to the lack of awareness and understanding. The participants had an understanding that the university

needs to ensure ethics is not seen as a tick box exercise, but as a process designed to help and encourage the integrity of research.

4.2 Ethics external responses

There is an understanding from the participants of the term ‘ethics’, some understanding of ethical research and ethical procedures when developing products and services and the need for ethics. The participants have an appreciation that ethics is fundamental to research, gaining more opinions of what is ethical is essential to avoid bias. The participants display an understanding of the type of organisation that use ethics and the systems they have in place. Noted was the types of internal ethics policies that are used by the university and the importance of ethics in the design, build, testing, and marketing of medial/social care devices/services and why it should be considered at all stages and all decisions. There is an awareness of change in motivation since recent scandals, there is an acknowledgement of the importance of having ethics for medial/care. The participants suggested “ethics implementation equals better institutional practice, better societal outcomes”.

Response suggest the participants are somewhat unsure of ethical processes outside of that is happening in the universities. There is some limited knowledge of who to contact within an institution regarding ethics, participant highlighted this is based on already established relationships, so the more people you know the better.

The participants display in their responses that they have had some conversations around ethics with institutions and the NHS, in either current project or projects they have worked on in the past. Moving forward it is suggested to keep co-creation simple, “don’t give busy people more work to do”.

4.3 Science education internal responses

Display is an awareness of knowing that organisations, institutions and individuals facilitate science education, this includes an awareness of outreach programs. The responses suggest participants understand the importance of science education and are interested in what advantages can be made to enhance science education. There is an understanding of the important role the institute plays within society and the community and the level of trust that is place on academia and scientists. The responses suggest the participants have an understanding of how enhancement of engagement and shared education is “crucial” to ensure the relationship between science and society is protected. The participants had an understanding that good research is “open, transparent and have finding that are communicated and shared widely”.

Responses indicate that some disciplines have less insight into science education, with a limited basic knowledge. Furthermore, some participants have a lack of knowledge of the implantation of science education, with most participants having no awareness of any science education policy within the university. A few participants felt they could not comment on how motivated the university is to implement science education, also participants had some limited knowledge of how to implement science education within their own role.

4.4 Science education external responses

Displayed is an awareness that science education is available, with some of the participants mentioning how they have worked with the university in promoting the diffusion of research. There is an understanding of STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) days, which usually cater for sixth form and secondary school children. It is noted these events educate participants about careers in science and research, rather than display what research is happening in the university and how the community can get involved. The responses show some limited understanding of what science education is implemented by institutions, however there is some awareness of science education policies. The participants display an understanding of the benefits of implementing science education, including, societal benefits, development of critical thinking, analysis skills, being able to draw conclusions and problem solving.

The responses show a lack of understanding of the content of science education with some unable to respond to the science education questions. The participants also suggested that the strain on resources at the university, affects science education. In the responses there were some mixed responses on who to contact regarding the implementation of science education.

5. Focus group outcome summary

The responses to the focus group evaluation form suggest the participants felt there was a good mix of view point during the focus group, highlighting “it was good to hear from different groups and stakeholders on involving society in research”. The participants felt the focus group was a good opportunity to discuss views and opinions, and led to a better understanding of ethics. It was also noted it was good to hear what issues are currently being faced in RRI and OS.

When asked if they found the activities pre and during the focus group useful, participants responded suggesting the first questionnaire gave them “time to reflect on their own view as a researcher. Participants also reported they found the activities very informative and raised issues that were not previously considered. Through discussions it was highlighted the challenges in creating policies and that ethics must be central to any research. The participants also noted the need to encourage more disciplines within institutions to invite their participants as the researcher, not just a participant. There is some limited awareness for RRI and OS pre-focus group the responses show some interest in RRI and OS, however participants pointed out that more clarity and definition is needed in these areas. Finally most participants can see the benefits of RRI and OS within their current role.

On the evaluation form all participants agreed the focus group was useful, all participants, with the exception of 1 (for initial questionnaire) also found the activities pre and during the focus group useful, and all but one participants said they are interested in RRI and OS. 6 out of 13 stated they did not have an awareness of RRI and OS before the focus group, with an average of 4.5 on the 5 point scale agreeing with the aims of the project. Participants gave an average of 4.1 out of a 5 point scale when rating the usefulness of RRI and OS

6. Follow-up interview summary

We conducted a mixture of face to face and telephone one-to-one interviews with each of the participants to follow up on matters discussed during the focus group. Their responses were noted (not recorded) and are summarised below.

When asked what collaboration opportunities are available within the university and industry? The participants responded suggesting, the university share resources and knowledge in departmental collaboration, however this is often with colleges you already know limiting these collaborations. Also noted was how the REF framework has increased the collaboration work conducted in the university, however each university has different “approaches cultures, policy, an individuals, individuals make the difference”. Participants highlighted that within the university there are school and outreach programs that encourage knowledge exchange, as well as some funders require collaboration with other universities or companies to be noted in the application for funding process. The university is also linked to charity organisations and the NHS. Participants suggest “there are lots of opportunities for collaboration work.

Participants went on to state, collaboration with industry is less established than that between higher education institutions however, this is improving. Within the university there are lots of pockets that are just not joined up, this could lead to missed opportunities for collaborative working. Highlighted was the assumption that universities can be closed making it hard for outside companies to gain access to collaborate, with a lack of collaboration leading to solutions to problems being constructed without talking to the relevant stakeholders. Participants noted this lone research and innovation design can equal a waste of the product, research and time if it is not well received by society. Co-design means the end user is able to input ideas of what is needed at the early stages of the research. This type of collaboration requires re-visit to all stakeholders at multiple times in the process.

Some participants sate they would not know how to start a collaboration unless they had already established connections within the university. It was also noted by participants that there needs to be more of a balance in research motivation, currently it is more towards innovation not impact. Collaboration between all stakeholders is needed for thinking and exploring before the design stage of the research. Also highlighted was that the most difficult engagement is the end user, it is vital they are made part of the process from the start and that within the university some disciplines are very isolated and collaboration is not part of the roles within the these disciplines, requiring a change in culture.

We then asked the participants, what would you view as the main benefits from working with the university on a project such as the 5G project or technology innovation? The participants suggested these collaborations give the stakeholders access to knowledge, resources, and networking. Also suggested was how working with the university can make the project attractive to investors and funders, as it provides the research with credibility, using the universities name in your research. The university can increase access to finical and physical resources. Collaboration with universities also offers engagement with creative researchers who will know how to distribute the innovation, how to inform people what is happening and other forms of communication. It is seen by the participants as a useful two way relationship, sharing knowledge and skills. Working with the university provides the opportunity to gain

access to ethically guided experiences. This is particularly useful for SME's (small to medium enterprises) who may not have their own policies.

According to the participants universities are often easier to collaborate with as they are not for profit driven, making them less competitive and having different motives to organisations. The university can test things quicker, they having working test beds, and staff and students to help with testing. They have resources and equipment such as laboratories, robots, and virtual reality equipment. These types of equipment can be expensive for companies to buy or hire. Participants also highlighted that working with the university can provide links with the NHS, Social policy and health and social science.

It was highlighted by the participants that the university cannot do everything on their own, SME's can help with problems and often help with the competition in a research project or innovation. The university can use connections in the social care sector to test the research with the end-users. The participants feel however, with all the pressures on university academics they often struggle to find the time to collaborate on research projects.

The participants were asked to consider what role civil society will play in collaborations between industry and the university? Highlighted was, collaborations will help keep society informed and raise awareness, society plays a key role in the co-creation of research projects, and they need to be part of the research from the start. Civil society can help keep the research grounded, managing expectations, guiding the research and ensure there is actual need for the research or innovation. The university is the tax payers' funds, they have an obligation to the tax payers to be open with the research that is being conducted. The data collected is then based on facts, real life scenarios.

The participants however suggested, it is not always clear to society what the university is and can do. As an outsider looking in it is hard to know what research is being conducted. The university need to show society who they are "these are our people and this is what we do." Participants also worry, would you get useful suggestions from society? Society should set challengers, not set what is researched.

The participants were asked to comment on how collaboration between all the stakeholders would help embed ethics and science education into projects such as the monitoring system and other 5G projects? The responses given suggests it will help increase knowledge transfer getting the public voice into the projects as well as having access to more resources which will enable better project design. These collaborations brings groups together, making sure no one is overlooked. It will ensure end product is stronger and not enforced on society.

In terms of ethics the participants suggested it will develop, honesty, trust, giving back to the people and respect for all stakeholders. It was also pointed out that ethics is more of a culture than a procedure. Highlighted was that these collaborations consider the human side of research not just the technology. Ensuring the participants are seen as people and not just a cohort. No one group working in isolation, being more open and bringing ethical opinions from all stakeholders making the project more inclusive.

The participants went on the state that people can get worried about the process, it needs to be explained better to ensure it is understood by all stakeholders that. It was also noticed by the participants of the study that researchers worry about being to open and their data being stolen.

Moving forward it was suggested that the views of the potential beneficiaries should be included on the ethics application forms. For this to be included some guidance would need to change in how and when we approach potential beneficiaries.

The participants were asked to suggest what policies or procedures would be required to better embed collaborative working to enhance ethics and science education? The participants mentioned a collaborative section is already included on some funding forms. This is a space for researcher to included details on how they are going to collaborate on the research project with other stakeholders. The participants also mentioned that all policies and procedures have an ethics element to them.

The participants questioned the effectiveness of policies and procedures suggesting the lack of time to keep up to date with them and reread when needed would make them hard to have an impact. Keeping the policy short and easy to understand would help to overcome this challenge. It was also highlighted policies and procedures outline what you can't do not what you can do. Policies and procedures can be hard to enforce and manage especially when collaborating if different organisations have different policies and procedures to follow.

Moving forward the participants suggested an undergraduate training course to reinforce ethical thinking from entry to university. An open access policy and an ethics code of conduct was also highlighted to be beneficial to the research community. Other participants suggested have an operating model or memorandum of understanding rather than policies or procedure maybe more useful. No matter what is used, it was stressed by participants that when dealing with the public, the document needs to highlight the importance of privacy, data storage and GDPR.

Finally I asked the participants during a workshop on ethics and science education what would you be expected to learn and what activities would you like to see? The participants highlighted that they wanted more clarity and definition on RRI and how to embed it within their roles. There was also the suggestion of defining ethics and the different types of ethics that are used in the university and society. The participants asked for case studies and scenarios to better enhance understanding and they wanted to fully understand the challenges faced by other researchers and discuss how these can be overcome. Also noted was that they wanted the workshop to be a hands on workshop with lots of table discussions, two way learning and practical activities.

7. Workshop summary

Participants were asked to create a model representing their understanding of ethical research and innovation using construction bricks and modelling clay. They identified the following themes; coordination, accountability, responsibility, difference, change, disconnect, and education. During discussions the participants recognised that there was a need for learning by

doing and that the process was messy. Questions were raised about the perception of ethics asking ‘ethical – for whom?’ Similarly, questions were raised about the use of the word ‘impact’ asking who the impact was aimed at and for what purpose. The theme of relationships was identified from the angle of relationship building and of relationship breakdown, leading to a discussion about the positives and negatives of all voices being heard

The second element of the workshop discussed the similarities differences between the RRI models. The Similarities presented themselves as, struggle to include all elements of RRI, achieving a balance between inputs and outputs, all the models created included people and there was a recognition of the need to take into account everything. Highlighted what that Communication is key, acknowledging other people’s views, and civil society needs to be included as a stakeholder. The Differences were noted as, approaches to research and what RRI meant, single researcher Vs. Teams of researchers/practitioners and, how RRI was being embraced and embedded.

The workshop concluded with a discussion about the participants learning, what they need to consider going forward and their next steps. Participants identified that they needed to ensure their research was ethical and responsible but there was pressure from outside influences such as fake or false news reporting. There was also a recognition of the need to be conscious of confirmation bias in our research and the influence of “right opinion” vs. “the other point of view” however uncomfortable that might feel.

Moving forward participants identified that they might consider a memorandum of agreement to increase equality within projects and to ensure there was a two-way dialogue between stakeholders and researchers, checking understanding on both sides. Participants also recognised that they might need to consider any IP implications, confidentiality and who needs to be involved at each stage of the research. There was also recognition that research needs to include a ‘lived’ experience and junior members of civil society.

Participants left the workshop considering the legal frameworks for their research.

8. Second questionnaire summary

Internal and external participants (n=10, external n=6, internal n=4) took part in a self-report questionnaire on FIT4RRI ethics and science education, this was a replica of the first questionnaire that was sent out at the start of the project, the purpose of this was to test development in understanding and changes in opinions.

When thinking ethics the participants rated their understanding on a five point scale (1=not at all aware, 5= highly aware) answering three questions on their understanding of ethics the results show, external participants had a high level of ethics understanding (M=14) as well as internal participants also displaying a high level of understanding (M=13.5).The participants were asked, in the same way, their understanding of science education. For both internal (M=9) and external (M=11.6). The results show this was lower than their ethics understanding. The participants were then asked to rate their motivation of the implementation of ethics, internal (M=12.5) external (M=14.1) and their motivation of the implementation of science education,

internal (M=12.7) external (M=12). The results show the motivation to implement ethics was higher than that of science education for external participants however, was slightly lower for internal participants.

Table one shows the mean and standard deviation for the understanding of ethics and science education, both internally and externally and the motivation to implement ethics and science education also both internally and externally.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation for the understanding and motivation of implementation of ethics and science education.

	Mean	SD
Understanding of ethics – External	14	1.5
Understanding of ethics – internal	13.5	2.3
Motivation to implement ethics – external	14.1	1.6
Motivation to implement ethics – internal	12.5	2.5
Understanding of science education – external	11.6	1.9
Understanding of science education – internal	9	2
Motivation to implement science education – external	12	2.9
Motivation to implement science education – internal	12.7	0.5

After each question the participant were asked to expand on their point score. Below is a summary of their responses.

8.1 Ethics Internal responses

In their responses the participants’ state since taking part in the FIT4RRI project they are much more aware of the ethical issues faced by researchers, and are more aware of gaps in their own knowledge of ethical practices. Participants also stated since taking part in the project they have become “much more aware of the ethics policies in the institution” and would know who to contact in terms of ethics implementation. The participants suggested there is an increase in knowledge across all disciplines in the university, however the depth of knowledge can vary depending on role, as some roles within the university do not come into contact with ethical implications.

It was highlighted by the participants that there is a department within the university that is required to raise awareness of ethics across the institution, however this department is under resourced and staff find it hard to find the time to complete this fundamental task to its fullest. As well as this it was noted that academics often have such high workloads that they may struggle to engage with the university communication channels, therefore finding out about ethical issues may be compromised. Participants suggest academic leadership are highly motivated to implement high standards of research ethics. However, there is very little institutional support on the administrative leadership side.

The participants suggest that implementing ethics sounds like hard, but necessary work. Going on to highlight the barriers to the implementations of research ethics could come down to the individuals involved in the process. Individuals with a lack of experiences of research ethics can see the process as unnecessary, and could demonstrate resentment and disengagement from the process. On the other hand the culture in some disciplines who have a lot of experience in research ethics, could see the process as bureaucratic and unnecessary because of their extensive experience. For this group, trying to implement change from the top down is demotivating. Highlighted was the fact that academics are faced with a huge number of competing priorities, so some might see ethics as an un-important, additional administrative burden.

Moving forward it is highlighted by participants that the university has an obligation to implement good research ethics. This will improve the quality of research across the university.

8.2 Ethics external responses

The participants show an understanding of the importance of ethics, especially when working in the medical or healthcare sector, stating it is “an essential part of any project”. There is an awareness of the university and hospitals having ethics procedures, understanding that “implementation is vital for institutions”. There is an understanding of the “vital importance of strong ethics policies in scientific institutions” and how important it is to establish ethics early in collaboration processes. The participated displayed an understanding of how the universities are motivated to implement ethics in research, and have an awareness of the ethics committees within the university.

Participants expressed being unsure on how ethical decisions are made and implemented within the university, and that some universities see ethics as red tapes to getting things done. It was also highlighted by participants that some organisations do not make all their ethical decisions public knowledge.

Moving forward it was suggested that research needs to be ethical sound and that the ethics within the research and ethics as a whole needs to be regularly reviewed. It was also suggested that all SME’s need ethics to work in the public sector. It was stated by some participants that through their own contacts they would be able to source someone within the university to discuss the implementation of ethics.

8.3 Science education internal responses

Participants state a greater understanding of science education has developed following participation in the FIT4RRI project, as well as how science education is communicated in research projects and the different perspectives involved. The participants have also stated since taking part in the project their motivation to implement science education has increased. There is an awareness of outreach programs offered by the university among the participants. The participants acknowledge that part of good research practices is having “open, transparent finding which are communicated and shared widely”. Most of the participants felt they would know who to contact about implementing science education in their role.

Participants state to their knowledge there are no policies for science education. Furthermore the participants suggest there is a lack of visible signs of intentional motivation to implement science education. Participants suggest further investigation into how the university is implementing science education may be needed.

Moving forward it is suggested by the participant that sharing scientific literacy to the general population is crucial in helping to solve the global problems of today.

8.4 Science education external responses.

The participants have shown an awareness of science education with some involvement in STEM day and science education programmes. Some participants outlined the work they have done with schools and colleges to further knowledge and real world education for students. The participants understand the importance of science education stating “the more public understanding of science is improved the better for society”. Furthermore it is suggested that the “development of industry depends on the diffusion of scientific and factual information”.

Some participants expressed limited knowledge of the implementation of science education courses, with participants detailing how they have limited involvement in science education implementation. Highlighted was the lack of awareness of how the universities communicate the importance and benefits of science education. It was also noted by the participant that other than what the universities offer there is not much more science education available to the public, and there was limited knowledge as to who to contact in the university to discuss science education implementation.

9. Comparing the first and second questionnaire.

The participants were asked to fill out the same questionnaire at the start and the end of the process. This was to measure developments in understanding and changes in opinions. 10 out of 13 participants took part in both questionnaires, with all showing some increase in knowledge on the 5 points system, however some participants did mark lower on this scale the second time filling it in. For ethics understanding, ethics motivation, science education understanding and science education motivation each of the 10 participants answered three questions making a total of 30 answers. The changes in responses show for ethics awareness 9 answers increased on the 5 point scale with 4 answers decreasing. For ethics motivation 7 answers increased with 3 answers decreasing. For science education awareness 15 answers increased with one answer decreasing. Finally for science education motivation 13 answers increased with 7 answers decreasing.

10. Lessons learnt

The project would have benefited from gaining ethical approval soon, this would have led to more, earlier interaction with stakeholders allowing time to build trusting relationships. Through building these relationships it may have become more apparent as to how to better motivate stakeholders to engage with all aspects of the project and even increase participation.

On reflection the lack of awareness of the need or ethics may have contributed to the low uptake in participants. Sharing knowledge on the importance of ethics and detailing the benefits of taking part better may have helped the situation. A number of participants could not make the focus group or workshop, these were mainly beneficiaries of the monitoring system, care providers who would be using health promoting technology. These views were vital to the process so I arranged a small number of one-to-one meetings in a better suited location. Having the focus groups or workshops in a range of locations may have been helpful to these participants.

10.1 Main blockers of quadruple helix co-creation

- Money
- Public perceptions
- Culture
- Time
- Why is it needed
- Lack of awareness
- Trust
- Communication

10.2 Proposed consensus strategies and co-creation approaches/frameworks

We feel this has been answered in the participants' responses summaries above

10.3 Most relevant RRI practices from WP1 and WP2 for the experiment

After reading the reports from WP1 and WP2 we decided to focus on openness, ensuring that the participants of our study understood the importance of being open with their research. Having a multi-actor process was also an important element we wanted to convey to our participants. Helping them understand that having more actors involved will improve the quality of research and innovation process. As part of the processes we wanted to explore what networking opportunities are available to the university, industry and civil society. We asked the participants what types of collaboration they are involved with or feel they have the opportunity to become involved in with these stakeholder groups. This type of collaboration working and networking will increase contributions from all stakeholders, and align science and innovation with societal needs.

10.4 Institutional changes required to fully embed the chosen RRI pillars

It has been identified that better training across more disciplines is needed within the university. A training course for post graduate research students is being developed with the hopes to be

tested in the coming term. The success of this course will ensure that more (ideally all) post graduate research students have an understanding of RRI and can therefore embed it in their research.

10.5 Policy support/changes required to properly embed RRI in the ongoing research with the involvement of the quadruple helix

During the focus group the participants were asked to suggest what policies would be needed to better embed RRI. In groups the participants noted that policies should have a value based approach, have clear guidelines and be easy to understand. Further suggested what for policies to be meaningful and meet trust expectations of the public, it needs to outline how researchers communicate their research and why and how to achieve this. Also highlighted was that policies should state that ethical approval will cover collaborators, this has been an issues on some project participants have taken part in and they felt this addition would save time.

10.6 Any issues/constrains notice during the experiment implementation (i.e procedural issues)

Some early problems with delays in gaining ethical approval. This was just a time frame problem as it was submitted at a busy time in the university.

We were unable to get the beneficiaries of the product to take part in most aspects of the project. This was due to them not having time to spare out of their day to day to attend the focus group or workshop. I was able to visit two care organisations for one-to-one interviews their responses are summarised with the other participants.

11 Next steps

- Community events.
- Ethics training courses for PGR students.
- Open research event
- Phd conference training
- Publish articles on the research conducted
- Seek funding to sustain the FIT4RRI efforts

Appendix A – Experiment KPIs

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	TOOL
RELEVANCE		
Scope of the experimentation		
R1 RRI pillars focused upon*	This is a quantitative indicator. It refers to the 5 RRI/OS pillars and the governance of RRI/OS.	2 pillars
R2 RRI best practices considered for assessment of their potential implementation in the ongoing research*	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to the best practices developed under the experiment's design phase which are considered (by the organisation or other relevant actors) relevant and thus deserving to be implemented.	The best practices are: Openness Multi-actor process Improve the quality of research and innovation process Increase networking opportunities Increase contribution from all stakeholders Align science and innovation with societal needs
R3 Connection with existing policies/measures developed by the organisation	This is a qualitative indicator. The question is understanding to what extent the experiment is connected with and takes into consideration the existing policies at the organisation level . For example, if there is a budget heading the experiment could refer to, if there is a policy context where the experiment could be framed, etc.	Ethics policy, public engagement policy, impact case studies, social impact policy, business engagement, consultancy scheme, EU investment
Agreement		
R4 Degree of agreement of the beneficiaries about the aims of the experiment	This is a quantitative indicator (a 5-point agreement scale may be used) but also qualitative elements can be collected.	– Interviews with the beneficiaries Ethics – high agreement in university – 5 Science education Care providers – 2 End users – 4 (not so much about ethics but about monitoring)
R5 Degree of agreement of other concerned actors in the organisation about the aims of the experiment	This is a quantitative indicator (a 5-point agreement scale may be used) but also qualitative elements can be collected.	University – 5 9 of them scored - 5 4 scored - 3 (Internal and external)
R6 Degree of agreement of quadruple helix actors	This is a quantitative indicator (a 5-point agreement scale may be	Liverpool city council – agreement 5

about the aims of the experiment	used) but also qualitative elements can be collected.	9 of them scored - 5 4 scored - 3 (Internal and external)
Mobilisation of internal actors		
R7 Active involvement of the organisation's management *	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at understanding to what extent the experiment succeeded in involving the top management at the relevant level (e.g., department level, HR offices, University board, etc.). Involvement can be assessed in different ways (participation in meetings and initiatives, meetings with the team, technical and organisational support, etc.)	Ethics committee structure- senior management, PRO VCs, heads of departments, members of ethics committees, Council, ethics committee in December (no ad hoc meetings)
R8 Active involvement of researchers *	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at understanding to what extent the experiment succeeded in involving researchers. Involvement can be assessed in different ways (participation in meetings and initiatives, support to the planned actions, etc.)	Yes – the primary ones + extended - + Industry 4.0 researchers + PhD students are involved in the project.
Mobilisation of external actors		
R9 Active involvement of quadruple helix actors*	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at understanding to what extent the experiment succeeded in involving quadruple helix actors. Involvement can be assessed in different ways (participation in meetings and initiatives, support to the planned actions, etc.)	Full engagement

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	TOOL
EFFECTIVENESS		
Implementation process		
E1 Actual implementation of the planned actions	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at assessing to what extent the experiment sticks to established plans. Deviations not necessarily refers to problems in the implementation process, but can also be an effort to make the experiment more effective or relevant to the context.	On time
E2 Compliance with planned schedules and deadlines	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at assessing to what extent the experiment sticks to established plans. Deviations not necessarily refers to problems with the implementation process,	On time

	but can also be an effort to make the experiment more effective or relevant to the context.		
Beneficiaries			
E3	Match between the number of beneficiaries planned/ number of actual beneficiaries	This is a quantitative indicator, the significance of which may vary according to the experiment .	Full match.
E4	Match between the type of intended beneficiaries and the type of the actual beneficiaries	This is a qualitative indicator, the significance of which may vary according to the experiment.	Full match.

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	TOOL	
IMPACT			
Objective impact – Institutional agreement			
I1	Number of quadruple helix consensus solutions (common agreed plans/steps) for supporting the embedment of RRI *	This is a quantitative indicator. It refers to the level of involvement of external players in the experiment through formal arrangements. This indicator could be also relevant for the dimension “Sustainability”	2 - Going out to the community and speaking with people- was agreed in the focus groups More emphasis on trainings and the means of training (better quality trainings)
Objective impact – Expected changes			
I2	Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes at the level of the research group/department/quadruple helix actors directly involved with the experiment	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to any significant change in the life of the organisation at the relevant organisational level directly due to the experiment. Any modification observed during and after the implementation phase deserves anyhow to be recorded.	Internal exercises for the PGR school Revision of the ethics strategy
I3	Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes in parts of the organisation not directly involved with the experiment	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to indirect effects of the experiment on other parts of the organisation, which can be viewed as a precursor of an embedment process of RRI/OS.	After the workshop internal participant agree to embed RRI participants into their roles within their current positions.
I4	Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes in external organisations (quadruple helix actors)	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to indirect effects of the experiment on other parts of the organisation, which can be viewed as a precursor of an embedment process of RRI/OS.	In the evaluations from the workshop external participants stated they would use RRI principals moving forward within their organisations.
Objective impact – Unexpected effects			

I5	Occurrence of unexpected effects concerning the involved actors (e.g. unplanned introduction of new norms, policies, or procedures; establishment of new networks or groups as an effect of the experiment; etc.)	This is a qualitative indicator. Unexpected effects can be both positive or negative, i.e., supporting or hindering the embedment of RRI/OS. When positive, they are considered an important precursor of an embedment process of RRI/OS.	We will have a follow up on this matter. No unexpected effects up to date.
Objective impact – Multiplicative effects			
I6	Observation of result/best practice multiplication in the quadruple helix ecosystem generated through the experiment *	This is a qualitative indicator. Differently from the previous one, which are mainly interested in new actions or reactions, this indicator should capture larger forms of mobilisation on RRI/OS occurred beyond the scope of the experiment.	No results as yet, however further dissemination may provide some observational effects beyond the scope of the experiment.
Objective impact – Communication impacts			
I7	Increased visibility of the experiment within the organisation	This indicator is of a qualitative nature and refers to the presence of information on the experiment or on RRI/OS related issues in, e.g., institutional websites, meetings, newsletters, internal communication channels, and the like. The more the experiment is known, the more is likely to have an impact on the organisation.	Yes – internal communication, departments, RRI training in PGR studies Focus groups with SMEs
I8	Increased visibility of the experiment outside the organisation	This indicator is of a qualitative nature and refers to the presence of information on the experiment or on RRI/OS-related issues because of the experiment outside the organisation.	Focus groups with SMEs
Subjective impact – Degree of agreement with the experimentation			
I9	Degree of satisfaction of the beneficiaries about the activities carried out	This is a quantitative indicator (5-point scale).	Very high satisfaction (4/5).
I10	Degree of satisfaction of the Teams about the activities carried out	This indicator can be qualitative and can include different aspects.	Good level of satisfaction (3.5/5)
I11	Degree of satisfaction of the actors internal to the organisation about the activities carried out	This is a quantitative indicator (5-point scale).	Good levels of satisfaction (see the report).
I12	Degree of satisfaction of the quadruple helix actors about the activities carried out	This is a quantitative indicator (5-point scale).	Good levels of satisfaction (see the report).
I13	Number of RRI best practices evaluated and highly rated by the stakeholders *	This can be a quantitative indicator, even though some qualitative aspects should be anyhow considered (e.g., motivations at the basis of the rating outputs).	(4) - Inclusion, Open Access, Ethics of research RRI Toolkit from the FOSTER Platform
Subjective impact – Changes in the perception of RRI/OS			
I14	Changes in the interest in RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	This is a qualitative indicator. It should measure to what extent the experiment raised a greater interest towards RRI/OS,	This has been included in the report

	regardless to the orientation (positive or negative), in the internal actors. It is also possible to make the indicator quantitative using a 5-point scale. However, qualitative aspects should be also considered.	
I15 Changes in the interest in RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	This is a qualitative indicator. It should measure to what extent the experiment raised a greater interest towards RRI/OS, regardless to the orientation (positive or negative), in the internal actors. It is also possible to make the indicator quantitative using a 5-point scale. However, qualitative aspects should be also considered.	This has been included in the report
I16 Changes in the awareness of RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Awareness refers here to the attitude of the actors to consider RRI/OS as an important aspect of the life of the organisation interviews are part of. Therefore, awareness refers to a positive orientation towards RRI/OS. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.	This has been included in the report
I17 Changes in the awareness of RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Awareness refers here to the attitude of the actors to consider RRI/OS as an important aspect of the life of the organisation interviews are part of. Therefore, awareness refers to a positive orientation towards RRI/OS. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.	This has been included in the report
I18 Changes in the perceived usefulness of RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Usefulness can be considered as a precursor of a future mobilisation in support to the implementation of RRI/OS. It refers to the recognition of the capacity of RRI/OS to address problems that the actors are already dealing with. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.	Included in the report
I19 Changes in the perceived usefulness of RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Usefulness can be considered as a precursor of a future mobilisation in support to the implementation of RRI/OS. It refers to recognition of the capacity of RRI/OS to address problems that the actors are already dealing with. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.	Included in the report
<i>Subjective impact – Orientation towards future involvement</i>		

I20	Explicit orientation to promote/ get involved in future RRI/OS-oriented activities of each internal actors	This is a qualitative indicator which can be also expressed in quantitative ways through 5-point scales. Differently from usefulness, this indicator assess the personal involvement of the actors in RRI/OS	Mostly yes (12 out of 13)
I21	Explicit orientation to promote/ get involved in future RRI/OS-oriented activities of quadruple helix actors	This is a qualitative indicator which can be also express in quantitative way through 5-point scales. Differently from usefulness, this indicator should measure the personal involvement of the actors in RRI/OS	Mostly yes (12 out of 13)

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	TOOL	
SUSTAINABILITY			
<i>Recommendations produced</i>			
S1	Policy change recommendations *	This indicator is aimed at measuring the capacity of the experiment to “launch” possible future RRI/OS-oriented policies at the relevant organisational level. This indicator is of a qualitative nature	Ethics and PGR (internal)
S2	Organisational change recommendations *	This indicator is aimed at measuring the capacity of the experiment to “launch” possible future RRI/OS-oriented changes in organisational practices at the relevant organisational level. This indicator is of a qualitative nature	Ethics board.
<i>Institutional links and agreements</i>			
S3	Creation of links with key players not previously engaged in the implementation of the experiment	This indicator is intended to assess the capacity of the experiment to activate new possibly permanent social configurations and cooperation relationships. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	Link with the research support department and a community engagement event.
S4	Creation of stable links with other bodies involved in the implementation of the experiment	This indicator is intended to assess the capacity of the experiment to activate new possibly permanent social configurations and cooperation relationships. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	Link with the research support department and a community engagement event.
S5	Industry/RFPO proposals for collaboration with researchers *	This indicator is intended to assess if the experiment led to the establishment of clear or possibly formal new cooperation programmes. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	Yes (interest has been received for joint proposals).
S6	Society-driven proposals for collaboration with researchers *	This indicator is intended to assess if the experiment led to the establishment of clear or possibly formal new cooperation	Possibility of more after community event has been held

		programmes. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	
<i>Institutionalisation processes within the organisation</i>			
S7	Identification/acquisition of new resources to continue the activities or parts of them	This is a qualitative indicator aimed at assessing to what extent the organisation or other internal and external actors are leaned to invest on RRI/OS in the future. This can be a composite set of indicators, also including quantitative indicators (e.g., quantity of resources, number of sources, etc.)	Not yet
S8	Establishment of institutional arrangements to make the new operational setups activated by the actions definitive (e.g., institutionalisation of scholarships, drafting of internal regulations that establish procedures to access certain benefits, etc).	This is a qualitative indicator aimed at assessing to what extent the experiment already led to the establishment of new permanent solutions inspired to RRI/OS at the relevant organisational level (department, organisation, etc.).	In the PGR